

IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOL USAGE ON STUDENT COGNITION ACROSS ACADEMIC FIELDS

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The use of AI in education is rapidly expanding, raising important questions about its effects on students' cognitive development and academic performance.

Aim. This study aims to analyze the impact of AI tools on general cognitive performance and problem-solving abilities among students in different academic fields.

Materials & Methods. The investigation targets three disciplines: Medicine, Economics, and Information Technology, comparing AI users and non-users. This study included 150 students (50 from each field) with a mean age of 18.33 ± 1.13 years. Participants were categorized as AI users and non-users. Cognitive abilities were assessed using the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA), which measured general cognitive performance (normal or low), and the Frederick test, which evaluated reflective problem-solving skills (scores of 3–2 as good, 1–0 as low). Descriptive statistics including means, standard deviations, and percentages were used to analyze cognitive performance outcomes.

Result. Field-specific analysis showed significant differences in cognitive performance. Among Medicine students, AI users had a higher mean MoCA score (28.12 ± 1.47) than non-users (27.40 ± 1.72), with 44% and 32% demonstrating normal cognitive abilities, respectively. In Economics, AI users scored higher on the MoCA (27.94 ± 1.55) compared to non-users (26.90 ± 1.88), with 68% of users and 56% of non-users showing normal cognitive ability. IT students showed the greatest positive impact, with AI users scoring a mean of 28.02 ± 1.68 on the MoCA and 78% demonstrating normal cognitive abilities, compared to non-users who scored 27.34 ± 1.84 , with 54% in the normal range. Similar trends were observed in the Frederick test, where AI users consistently outperformed non-users in reflective problem-solving tasks.

Conclusion. AI usage enhances general and reflective cognitive abilities, with notable field-specific variation: strongest in IT, moderate in Economics, and modest in Medicine. Effective integration of AI tools into academic programs can improve student thinking skills, especially when aligned with field-relevant tasks. These findings suggest that AI tools could improve cognitive skills in education and highlight the need for tailored AI integration strategies for different disciplines.